

Supplementary Material

Resveratrol Loaded Chitosan-Pectin Core-Shell Nanoparticles as Novel Drug Delivery Vehicle for Sustained Release and Improved Antioxidant Activities

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Keywords: resveratrol; core-shell nanoparticles; drug delivery, bioavailability, antioxidant activity.

4. Results and Discussions

Characterization of Resveratrol loaded Chitosan–Pectin nanoparticles

FESEM / EDX (Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy)

Figure ES1: FESEM image of RCP1 showing spherical morphology of Chitosan -Pectin core shell nanoparticles.

FETEM/SAED (Field Emission Transmission Electron Microscopy/ Selected Area Electron Diffraction)

Figure ES2: Lattice fringes seen in the HRTEM images of RCP3 at 2 nm and 5 nm scales

Figure ES3: Lattice fringes seen in the HRTEM image of RCP2 at 5 nm scale

Figure ES 4 Comparison of FT-IR spectra of RCP1, RCP2 and RCP3

Table ES1

Anova: Two-Factor with Replication

SUMMARY	72	77	86	Total
<i>59</i>				
Count	4	4	4	12
Sum	299.16	326.67	350.27	976.1
Average	74.79	81.6675	87.5675	81.34167
Variance	10.52307	31.76889	1.414892	41.66242
<i>77.32</i>				
Count	4	4	4	12
Sum	368.38	376.47	378.14	1122.99
Average	92.095	94.1175	94.535	93.5825
Variance	83.77697	25.90996	15.77363	35.45511
<i>Total</i>				
Count	8	8	8	
Sum	667.54	703.14	728.41	
Average	83.4425	87.8925	91.05125	
Variance	125.9752	69.00594	21.23681	